

Understanding 30 Years of Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) in the 2019 Indonesian Journal

Helpris Estaswara¹, Mashadi Said²

^{1,2}Faculty of Communication Sciences, Universitas Pancasila, Jakarta

ABSTRACT. This article examines 10 journals on Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) in Indonesia in 2019. Essentially, IMC consists of two core concepts, which have evolved into four stages of IMC implementation. The first concept, introduced in 1989, is known as the inside-out approach or tactical coordination of marketing communications. The second concept, emerging in 2004, is called the outside-in approach, encompassing internal support to external activities (Second Stage), application of information technology (Third Stage), and financial and strategic integration (Fourth Stage). Thus, this paper seeks to address: (1) What is IMC as described and applied?; (2) What communication elements are used?; (3) Is the brand the main message in the IMC program?; and (4) Is the IMC used inside-out or outside-in, and where are the boundaries? Using a systematic literature review method, the results indicate that IMC is marketing communication or promotion. The communication elements include advertising, personal selling, sales promotion, public relations, interactive marketing, corporate design, sponsorship, exhibitions, websites, merchandising, packaging, and social media. No articles used the brand as the main message in IMC, categorizing it as an inside-out approach since many did not involve the brand and only analyzed marketing communication or promotion. IMC in Indonesia does not align with the global development of the IMC concept but follows communication technology trends through the use of internet-based media, such as social media.

KEYWORDS. Integrated Marketing Communication, Communication Elements, Brand, Inside-Out, Outside-In

INTRODUCTION

From the 1990s to 2019, research on Integrated Marketing Communications (IMC) has been extensive and diverse, spanning various international (Kliatchko & Uttamchandani, 2023) and national journals (Estaswara et al., 2023). On one hand, there is research on IMC practices, and on the other, research on IMC concepts. Studies on IMC concepts focus on the conceptualization of IMC, including the precise definition of IMC, the evolution of its definition, and the IMC concepts that should be taught in higher education. Such research has been conducted by Swain (2004), Kitchen et al. (2004), and Kitchen and Schultz (2009). Meanwhile, studies on IMC practices explore how IMC is implemented, typically examining how companies use marketing communication or promotional elements to communicate their products and brands to consumers.

The practice of IMC has been ongoing since the initial conceptualization and development of the IMC concept in the late 1980s and early 1990s (Kliatchko, 2008, 2014). By the latter half of the 1990s, studies on the dissemination, strategic implementation, and global practice of IMC began to emerge (Grein & Gould, 1996; Eagle et al., 1999; Gould et al., 1999; Kitchen & Schultz, 1999). From 2000 onwards, more research on IMC perceptions and practices in various countries, such as Thailand, the Philippines, South Africa, Japan, Australia, South Korea, and China, has been initiated (Kliatchko, 2014), with studies in Indonesia beginning in 2006 (Estaswara, 2023).

On the other hand, research on concepts, such as issues related to the definition of IMC and its evolution (Kliatchko, 2008; Schultz & Patti, 2009), the definition of IMC and its practice, as well as the academic versus practitioner perspectives (Laurie & Mortimer, 2011), and strategic IMC (Kerr & Patti, 2015), has been widely published in various international journals. Additionally, systematic literature reviews of Scopus-indexed journals from the 1980s to the present, such as those by Šerić (2016) and Muñoz-Leiva et al. (2015), have examined IMC extensively. In Indonesia, research involving systematic literature reviews of various national journal articles has been conducted by Estaswara et al. (2023), focusing on the IMC concept and its implementation based on Indonesian journals in 2020.

There is a noticeable difference in both the type and quality of research between Indonesian journals and Scopus-indexed

Understanding 30 Years of Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) in the 2019 Indonesian Journal

journals. While Scopus-indexed journals have published studies on IMC concepts, Indonesian national journals generally focus on IMC practices. This is despite the fact that IMC practices have long ceased to be the main focus of various Scopus-indexed journals. The biggest challenges in IMC lie at the conceptual level (Kerr et al., 2008), alongside the current developments in communication media. Additionally, IMC, once viewed as coordinated communication based on "tools," is now regarded as a strategic process (Madhavaram et al., 2005).

On the other hand, considering that IMC was academically born in 1989 (Estaswara, 2016), then 2019 marked three decades of IMC worldwide. Generally, there hasn't been much discussion about these three decades of IMC in various journals, especially Indonesian ones. However, there are some writings, such as those by Kliatchko and Schultz (2014) and Kliatchko (2016), which delve into 20 years of IMC. Thus, this article conducts research in Indonesian journals in 2019 to commemorate 30 years of IMC. At the very least, over three decades, we can discern the progression of IMC in Indonesian journals as an academic representation, considering that Indonesian academics are among the driving forces of IMC, achieved through teaching and writing about IMC in various journals and books.

IMC emerged academically in 1989 (Estaswara, 2016; Kliatchko, 2005). At that time, IMC was viewed merely as the first generation, where all communication elements had to be integrated collectively. In this integration, no single element was deemed more important than the others; all were crucial, with only the context varying, as gleaned from data and environmental analysis. Subsequently, they were communicated effectively and efficiently to the target audience. This is what is referred to as the inside-out approach (Kerr et al., 2008). According to Estaswara (2016, p. 75), IMC in this first generation is described as, "still an external focus on managing various elements of marketing communications (promotional mix) in an integrated manner."

In 2004, the concept of the second generation of IMC emerged, where IMC had become integrated with business (Schultz & Schultz, 2004; Schultz & Kitchen, 2000; Estaswara, 2018). At this level, IMC was not only integrated into communication messages, but these messages had to be about the brand, hence IMC was also referred to as brand communication (Kliatchko, 2005, 2008). Moreover, the audience in IMC extended beyond just consumers to include all stakeholders, both internally and externally. Thirdly, communication technology had to be utilized to build databases, foster customer relationships, and serve as a basis for financial evaluation. Lastly, the communication elements employed in IMC encompassed all forms of communication, whether internal or external (Estaswara, 2016). This is what is termed as the outside-in approach (Kerr et al., 2008).

The Inside-out approach (Kerr et al., 2008; Schultz & Barnes, 1995) represents the initial stage in implementing IMC. This stage is characterized as tactical coordination of marketing communications, as companies tend to overlook customers and their needs, and are relatively simplistic in integrating various promotional elements such as advertising, publicity, sales promotion, personal selling, sponsorship marketing, and point-of-purchase communication, or IMC is merely understood as a promotional activity (Schultz & Schultz, 2004; Schultz & Kitchen, 2000). The concept of the "inside-out" approach, according to Kerr et al. (2008:513), is described as: "It begins with planning that takes place 'inside' the organization, and identifies what it hopes to achieve. This is commonly based on what has always been done 'inside', before trying to sell it 'outside' to the customer." Schultz and Barnes (1995:28) express that the "inside-out" approach involves traditional advertising campaigns or is defined as approaching marketing communication planning from the perspective of the marketer's needs.

Burnett and Moriarty (1998) responded to environmental changes by offering the concept of integration, which necessitates collaboration from all elements of the company to support organizational goals, thus establishing a flow of information across departments. Burnett and Moriarty's understanding (1998, p. 14) is essentially based on Schultz et al.'s (1993) perspective on IMC, which states that IMC is a new and comprehensive outlook where advertising, public relations, sales promotion, purchasing, employee communications, and so forth are viewed in an integrated manner. However, according to Estaswara (2008a), IMC requires marketing communication to always consider what is seen from the perspective of the consumer.

In the subsequent stages, the outside-in approach (Schultz & Schultz, 2004; Schultz & Kitchen, 2000) comes into play. The idea of IMC first emerged in 1993 (Kerr et al., 2008). According to Schultz and Barnes (1995, p. 35), the "outside-in" approach refers to IMC campaigns that approach marketing communication planning from the perspective of the consumer or customer's needs. Concerning the stages of IMC development, in the second stage, companies pay attention to consumers and study customer experiences. Companies actively observe what consumers want to see and hear, as well as when, where, and through which media (Kliatchko, 2008). At this stage, companies have a keen interest in various market research activities to support their communication efforts (Estaswara, 2008a). Companies begin to seek innovative new brand contacts via interactive alternative media (Shimp, 2003). All communication elements must speak with one voice. Coordination is crucial to generate a strong brand image and drive consumer purchasing actions. The essence of this second stage lies in internal support for external activities (Schultz & Schultz, 2004).

Next, the third stage is referred to as the application of information technology (Schultz & Schultz, 2004; Schultz & Kitchen, 2000). This stage also falls within the outside-in paradigm but is more advanced than the previous stage (Schultz & Schultz,

Understanding 30 Years of Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) in the 2019 Indonesian Journal

2004). Estaswara (2008a) reveals that companies invest in information resources to build segmented databases and restructure their organizations towards a consumer-focused and customer-driven approach. Companies undergo organizational transformation based on consumer orientation through the application of communication and information technology and database management to enhance performance in fostering customer loyalty. This effort involves building customer and prospect databases and effectively managing brand contact points to provide clear, precise, and swift measurements of customer purchasing behavior (Kliatchko, 2008). Consequently, various brand communication programs aimed at strengthening loyalty towards brand equity can be based on technology-driven evaluations (Schultz & Schultz, 2004).

Meanwhile, the final stage is termed financial and strategic integration (Schultz & Schultz, 2004; Schultz & Kitchen, 2000), which also falls within the highest level of the outside-in paradigm. Essentially, companies conduct evaluations of all IMC investments made, alongside assessing the effectiveness and efficiency of the overall IMC programs as the basis for planning subsequent IMC strategies (Schultz & Schultz, 2004). At this stage, companies have invested in information resources to build segmented customer databases. Therefore, if communication resources have been invested and measured according to actual customer behavior, financial returns can be achieved (Kitchen & Schultz, 1999).

Regarding brand communication and the initial outside-in stage, which is internal support for external activities (Schultz & Schultz, 2004), Michael Maskus, Head of Group Marketing at Allianz Group, is quoted as saying, "you have to deliver what you promise" (Burmam & Zeplin, 2005, p. 279). Building on this point, it can be said that a brand is a promise (Estaswara, 2008a). The brand is the company's promise, not the product's promise. It's the company's promise about the products (goods, services, and ideas) offered to the market. However, this promise must be fulfilled by the company. Avoid the occurrence of "high promise, low delivery" situations (Estaswara, 2008a). Therefore, to create a strong brand, the brand promise must be clear, consistent, and aligned with what it delivers (Aaker, 1996).

Regarding branding, the use of the phrase "brand communication" in the definition proposed by Kliatchko (2005) actually aligns with what Schultz and Schultz (2004) have envisioned with a more advanced understanding. According to Schultz and Schultz (2004), the concept of brand communication within IMC should move beyond and surpass the limitations of traditional or inside-out ideas. In this regard, Duncan (2002) states that IMC is a process to manage long-term profitable relationships with consumers or customers based on brand value through meaningful dialogue.

Thus, communication plays a strategic role in brand building. At the core of marketing communication lies the alignment of perceptions of brand value through interaction (Duncan, 2002; Estaswara, 2008a). Brand value is initially constructed through the formation of brand identity, which is then developed, managed, and integrated with IMC programs with the ultimate goal of creating brand equity. One of the significant reasons for the importance of IMC over the last three decades is that IMC plays a crucial role in the process of developing brand identity and strengthening brand equity. The challenge in implementing IMC lies in how to strategically use various communication tools with the right combination, enabling contact with consumers and effectively and efficiently conveying brand messages (Estaswara, 2008b).

Based on the elaboration above, this study aims to conduct a systematic literature review on IMC in articles of Indonesian Journals in 2019, marking the 30th anniversary of IMC, in order to ascertain: (1) What IMC is written and applied?; (2) What communication elements are used?; (3) Is the brand the main message in the IMC program?; and (4) Is the IMC used inside-out or outside-in, and where are the boundaries?

METHOD

This research utilizes literature review as the primary method. Literature review is a method capable of providing an overview of the development of a specific topic and enables researchers to identify the evolution of theories (Rowley & Slack, 2004). Additionally, literature review is a scholarly work that analyzes, synthesizes, and critically evaluates to provide a clear picture and information on a topic (Hart, 2018; Estaswara, 2023).

To maintain the precision of the methods used in the review process, a technique adopted from the PRISMA method (Transparent Reporting of Systematic Review and Meta-Analyses) is employed, starting from the search, screening, assessment of eligibility, to analysis. Additionally, the systematic review report adheres to a checklist provided to ensure its credibility. According to Sierra-correa & Kintz (2015), PRISMA offers three unique advantages: firstly, defining research questions that enable systematic research; secondly, identifying inclusion and exclusion criteria; and finally, examining scientific literature databases at specific intervals. Considering that PRISMA statements have been widely used in systematic reviews in the social sciences, this methodology is deemed suitable for use in this study.

The use of Google Scholar as the database in this research follows the approach taken in a previous paper (Estaswara, 2023). Although databases like EBSCO, Scopus, and Web of Science are the largest and most popularly used (Munoz-Leiva et al., 2015), Google Scholar is widely utilized by social scientists across various disciplines, including researchers in the fields of

Understanding 30 Years of Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) in the 2019 Indonesian Journal

communication and marketing. Therefore, relevant articles from this database cannot be disregarded in providing an overview of the concepts of IMC used after its 30 years of existence.

The search for articles on Google Scholar regarding journals from the year 2019 yielded 10 journals. Subsequently, the articles from these journals were read, understood, and comprehended. The inclusion criteria (accepted) and exclusion criteria (not accepted) can be seen in the table below.

Table 1. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Scope	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Concept	Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC), Integrated Marketing Communications, and IMC	Marketing Communication, Public Relations, Personal Selling, Sales Promotion, Direct Marketing, Sponsorship, and Point of Purchase
Language	Indonesian	Non-Indonesian
Manuscript	Scientific Articles	Theses, Dissertations, Books, Articles, Proceedings, Conference Papers
	Empirical Research	Non-Empirical Research
Time	2019	Before and after 2019
Text	Full Text	Abstract

Source: Author's Data 2002

Regarding the research questions, they can be explored through several factors that can be elucidated through the table

Understanding 30 Years of Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) in the 2019 Indonesian Journal

and diagram below.

Table 2. Scope, Research Questions, and Initial Codification

Scope	Research Questions	Initial Codification
IMC Concept	What IMC concepts are written and applied?	Added value, comprehensive planning, evaluation, communication elements, message clarity, message consistency, maximum impact, strategic process, cross-sectoral, marketing communication management process, multi-audience, dialogue, database, and implementation
	What communication elements are used?	Advertising, Public Relations, Personal Selling, Sales Promotion, Direct Marketing
Brand	Is the brand the main message in the IMC program?	The IMC message is about the brand
	Is the IMC used inside-out or still outside-in? Where are the boundaries?	Inside-out IMC integrates the promotion mix, while outside-in focuses on brand messaging, is two-way, uses communication technology, and is data-driven. The boundaries are outlined in the level of IMC development as explained by Schultz and Schultz (2004).

Source: Researcher's Data 2002

Diagram 1. Systematic Literature Review Diagram

Source: Adapted from Maher, 2009

Understanding 30 Years of Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) in the 2019 Indonesian Journal

Table 2. Obtained Journals

No.	Title	Journal	Authors
1	Building Brand Awareness for UMKM Products through Integrated Marketing Communication Strategy at Giant Ekstra Bintaro	Communication, Vol. 10(2), 174-192.	Taufan P. Gunadi
2	Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) Program Design at Naili DBS Hospital	Procuratio: Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen, Vol. 7(4), 484-495.	Try W. Sari & Rima Semiarty
3	Integrated Marketing Communication in Developing the Capacity of Rice Farmers in Banten Province	Jurnal Penyuluhan, Vol. 15(1), 111-119.	Johan D. Wetik, Amiruddin Saleh, Pang S. Asngari & Djuara P. Lubis
4	Integrated Marketing Communication and Brand Equity of Gojek Indonesia Branch Yogyakarta	Esensi: Jurnal Bisnis dan Manajemen, Vol. 9(1), 1-8.	Novia T. Lestari & Hani Sirine
5	Integrated Marketing Communication "Lemospirés Batik" in Attracting Consumer Purchase Interest	Jurnal Ilmu Komunikasi, Vol. 9(1), 69-84.	Cindy A. Kirana
6	Integrated Marketing Communication Strategy in Increasing Brand Awareness	IKON: Jurnal Ilmiah Ilmu Komunikasi, Vol. 13(2), 84-93.	Desy S. Anas
7	Integrated Marketing Communication Strategy for Marine Tourism to Shape Indonesia's Image as the World Maritime Axis	IKON: Jurnal Ilmiah Ilmu Komunikasi, Vol. 13(2), 153-180.	Virgitta Septyana
8	Integrated Marketing Communication Strategy of Sisikmelik Batik Gallery, Banyuwangi Regency	Jurnal Pendidikan Ekonomi, Vol. 13(2), 61-67.	Mita Lestari, Joko Widodo, & Mukhamad Zulianto
9	Integrated Marketing Communication Strategy of "Salatiga Movement (SM)" in Increasing Brand Awareness Among the People of Salatiga	Jurnal Komunikasi Universitas Garut: Hasil Pemikiran dan Penelitian, Vol. 5(2), 261-274.	Resva I. Kharisma & Lina S. Wijaya
10	Integrated Marketing Communication Strategy in Consumer Decision Making in the Field of Education Services	Prologia, Vol. 3(2), 423-432.	Feren A. Jasinta & Roswita Oktavianti

Source: Researcher's Compilation, 2022

RESULTS

Concept of IMC Written and Applied

In the article by Giant Ekstra, the concept of IMC is equated with promotion as IMC consisting of advertising, public relations, sales promotion, personal selling, and direct marketing, where these elements are considered important as a special blend when conducting marketing communication. The journal does not define IMC, only explaining IMC from the perspective of Kotler and Armstrong (2001). In its implementation derived from qualitative research, it only shows marketing communication strategies. This is consistent with the Lemospirés Batik article, where the article states that IMC is marketing communication. However, in its explanation, it only describes how marketing and communication are important, thus explaining through a communication diagram, namely encoding, transmission, decoding, and feedback. There is no IMC in its formulation, and it is only associated with the discussion of background related to the development of communication technology. How IMC is understood, in the article, does not provide explanation, and in its implementation based on qualitative methods, it only describes marketing communication.

Meanwhile, in the Gallery Batik Sisikmelik article, IMC is seen as a strategy, namely a communication process that requires planning, integration, and implementation of various communication elements based on Shimp's definition (2003). However, in its concept, it does not explain what IMC strategy is, and in its implementation based on qualitative methods, it only describes marketing communication. Similarly, in the Salatiga Movement article, IMC is viewed as a strategy, namely an effort to make all marketing communication activities produce a consistent image for customers. In this case, IMC is a marketing communication activity, where it communicates products, prices, and distribution through promotions based on IMC definition from Morrisson (2010). In its implementation, this article only describes marketing communication, without any explanation of strategy and IMC. While the article on Educational Services considers it as an IMC strategy, there is no definition and explanation of the strategy or IMC, only a brief description of marketing communication. This article with a mixed-methods approach only

Understanding 30 Years of Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) in the 2019 Indonesian Journal

describes marketing communication but does not explain its communication elements, but only consumers' views on educational services. Therefore, the three articles above can be considered as IMC seen as marketing communication for two articles, and consumer perspectives for the other article.

On the other hand, the article on Naili DBS Hospital views IMC differently from the Giant Ekstra article, where IMC is seen as a promising communication concept, more than just integration, coordination, and unification of communication instruments. IMC is no longer considered mere promotion, which is one-way or mass communication, but is seen as marketing communication that is personal, individual, and two-way based on Tjiptono's explanation (2008). In this journal, IMC is regarded as marketing communication but is personal and two-way, meaning consumers and producers can initiate communication where the communication is personal using internet media. However, in its application based on qualitative research, Naili DBS Hospital only describes marketing communication relying on internet media and direct communication.

Furthermore, the article on YAI Campus views IMC as a development of the promotional mix concept, where IMC must align customer perceptions with producers based on Estaswara's explanation (2008a). Therefore, the YAI Campus article prioritizes looking at customer perceptions of YAI Campus first, and then the producers respond and devise strategies. However, in the conceptualization and implementation, the YAI Campus article is only based on public relations with the PENCILS formulation, with no explanation related to IMC. Thus, IMC here is considered as public relations. However, in its implementation based on qualitative methods, it describes the PENCILS elements of public relations and consumer perspectives.

The article on Farmer Capacity also views IMC as merely a marketing communication of the promotion mix type. This perspective is broader than that of the Giant Ekstra article, placing IMC in line with the definition by Belch and Belch (2009), which sees it as a marketing communication planning concept that acknowledges the added value of a comprehensive plan evaluating the strategic role of communication disciplines. It integrates various disciplines to provide clarity, consistency, and maximum communication impact through the comprehensive integration of diverse messages. However, in its implementation based on quantitative methods, it does not refer to this definition and instead operates with promotion mix elements.

Similarly, the Gojek (Go-Ride) Yogyakarta article's IMC elaboration is based on the definition from the 4As, grounded in Duncan and Caywood (1996) and Kliatchko (1995, 1998). This defines IMC as a marketing communication planning concept that demonstrates comprehensive added value, evaluating the strategic role of various communication disciplines and combining them to create clear, consistent, and maximum communication impact. However, this article, which employs quantitative methods, applies promotion mix elements in its implementation.

The article on Maritime Tourism then draws on the concept of IMC from the book "IMC That Sells" (2011), where IMC is comprised of three circles; namely the discovery circle, intent circle, and strategy circle. Elaborating on the discovery circle leads to the analysis of both external and internal environments to unearth insights crucial for the brand. Subsequently, the intent circle is utilized to scrutinize issues and opportunities, thereby charting a direction and purpose aimed at promoting the brand. Finally, the strategy circle entails the formulation of brand strategies and tactics. While the discovery and intent circles are engaged, the strategy circle primarily focuses on strategically oriented marketing communication.

Communication Elements Used

In its implementation, the Giant Ekstra article utilizes communication elements, namely advertising, public relations, sales promotion, personal selling, and direct marketing as the primary components to explain IMC and discuss what Giant Ekstra sells through its marketing mix. However, it's noted that promotions and sales promotions are explained twice with almost the same pattern, indicating a lack of understanding regarding the difference between promotion and sales promotion. On the other hand, the RS Naili DBS article employs communication elements similar to those used by Giant Ekstra, but with the addition of WOM (Word of Mouth), interactive marketing, and events or experiences. In this article, the explanation of WOM does not align with the IMC program, as WOM refers to oral, written, or electronic person-to-person communication related to the benefits or experiences of purchasing or using products or services. Therefore, what consumers know about RS Naili DBS and communicate to their closest circles is not part of the IMC program.

In the Lemospirés Batik article, the same communication elements as Giant Ekstra are utilized, but with the addition of online marketing. However, in its implementation, not all elements are used; only advertising, public relations, and sales promotion are employed, with personal branding incorporated into personal selling and storytelling utilized in interactive marketing. Conceptually, the Lemospirés Batik article closely resembles the Maritime Tourism article but with the addition of interactive marketing. However, in its practical application, only advertising, personal selling, and public relations are utilized.

Moving on to the Salatiga Movement article, marketing communication elements cited from Kertajaya (2012) share similarities with Giant Ekstra but include events and experiences. In the Gallery Batik Sisikmelik article, although the marketing communication elements used are not explicitly mentioned, the implementation mirrors that of Giant Ekstra, with the addition of

Understanding 30 Years of Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) in the 2019 Indonesian Journal

internet marketing. This is similar to the approach taken in the Kapasitas Petani article, which doesn't explicitly discuss IMC but elaborates on advertising, events and experiences, sales promotion, interactive marketing, and direct marketing in its implementation.

Contrastingly, the Gojek (Go-Ride) article in Yogyakarta, employing a quantitative method similar to the Kapasitas Petani article, describes and implements communication elements such as sales promotion, personal selling, direct marketing, instructional material, corporate design, advertising, as well as public relations and publicity.

Furthermore, in the article on Maritime Tourism, the communication elements, referred to as the marketing communication mix, encompass similar aspects to those of Giant Ekstra. However, in practice, only advertising, personal selling, and public relations are carried out.

Moving on to the article on Educational Services, it states that IMC should encompass six communication elements based on Lovelock, Wirtz, and Mussry (2010): personal communication (WOM), advertising, sales promotion, public relations and publicity, educational materials (such as websites), and corporate design. While all of these elements are present in its implementation, regarding WOM, it is not considered a part of IMC.

Similarly, the article on YAI Campus outlines communication elements in IMC using the PR mix, known as PENCILS (Publications, Events, News, Community Involvement, Inform or Image, Lobbying and Negotiation, Social Responsibility). However, in its application, this aspect is not included.

Brand as the Primary Message

In IMC, the brand serves as the primary message. Therefore, communication elements must convey the brand message aimed at building and maintaining the brand, from introducing it, such as brand awareness and brand knowledge, to sustaining it, such as brand loyalty and brand equity.

In the Giant Ekstra article, the title itself indicates that IMC builds the brand, "Giant Ekstra Bintaro Builds Product Brand Awareness for MSMEs Through Integrated Marketing Communication Strategies", with the brand built being brand awareness. The article defines brand awareness as the ability of an individual to recognize or recall a brand that belongs to a product category. However, the results show that IMC has not yet been able to create brand awareness for MSME products, as they face stiff competition from imported products and are constrained by limited funds, preventing them from participating in all promotions. Even if these MSMEs were to participate in all promotions, it does not guarantee that their brand would be recognized as an "aware" brand.

The article titled "Integrated Marketing Communication Strategies in Increasing Brand Awareness" from YAI Campus shares similarities with the Giant Ekstra article, as both utilize IMC to enhance brand awareness using a qualitative approach. The difference lies in their communication elements, with the YAI Campus article employing a mix of public relations.

Regarding the outcomes of the IMC program aimed at boosting brand awareness for YAI Campus, consumers are able to recall the brand and provide their perception of YAI Campus as a university with comprehensive facilities, unique and modern buildings, strategic location, and affordable fees. However, the second outcome mentioned, which pertains to brand knowledge, is not elaborated upon in the article.

Meanwhile, the article on Gojek (Go-Ride) in Yogyakarta, employing a quantitative method and titled "Integrated Marketing Communication and Brand Equity of Gojek Indonesia Yogyakarta Branch," demonstrates that IMC has a significant impact on brand equity. Specifically, advertising, sales promotion, and corporate design positively influence brand equity. The title of the Gojek (Go-Ride) Yogyakarta article already indicates the presence of IMC and brand equity, showcasing how the company employs IMC to enhance brand equity.

The Maritime Tourism article reveals that IMC is undertaken to shape Indonesia's image as a global maritime axis. However, according to the article, image is defined as the public's message, impression, feeling, and perception of the company. Essentially, this study does not indicate whether IMC is successful in shaping this image. Furthermore, the article does not specify which image will be constructed through IMC; instead, it focuses on outlining IMC strategies and tactics derived from the book "IMC That Sells" through the discovery circle, intent circle, and strategy circle.

On the other hand, the Salatiga Movement article, focusing on a prominent modern dance community in Salatiga, aims to enhance brand awareness through IMC with the title "Integrated Marketing Communication Strategy of 'Salatiga Movement' in Enhancing Brand Awareness Among the Salatiga Community." This article is essentially aligned with the Giant Ekstra and YAI Campus articles concerning the IMC message, which is brand awareness. The research methodology employed is also similar to the Giant Ekstra and YAI Campus articles, being qualitative. The results indicate that awareness of the Salatiga community regarding the dance is still minimal. Despite the implementation of IMC programs to boost brand awareness, funding issues within

Understanding 30 Years of Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) in the 2019 Indonesian Journal

the community are identified as the primary obstacle. Consequently, this issue is not directly related to IMC.

Conversely, in other articles such as RS Naili DBS, Kapasitas Petani, Educational Services Sector, Lemospirés Batik, and Gallery Batik Sisik Melik, the IMC message does not revolve around a brand.

Inside-Out or Outside-In Approach and Their Boundaries

It's interesting to note that in the Giant Extra article, despite the aim to build brand awareness, there's no explanation of the brand and the IMC program or its message. In the public relations section, it only explains that Giant Ekstra creates consumer trust in the quality of the MSME products, thus fostering brand awareness in consumer understanding. However, the IMC message created is not about the brand, hence it's referred to as an inside-out approach or this stage is called tactical coordination of marketing communications.

Similarly, the YAI Campus article also reveals that IMC strategy is used to enhance brand awareness. It's noteworthy that the understanding of IMC is solely based on public relations (PENCILS) used to build brand awareness and interviewing the target audience, which forms the core of the research. In its elaboration, it talks more about the target audience and doesn't explain that the brand is the main message in the IMC program. Thus, the IMC used is only at the first stage, the inside-out approach or what is termed tactical coordination of marketing communications.

The Salatiga Movement article, aimed at building brand awareness, also mirrors the Giant Ekstra and YAI Campus articles regarding the IMC program, which should have a message about the brand. Indeed, brand awareness is explained along with its stages, but when discussing the communication elements in IMC, there's no elaboration on the brand. Even at the end of the discussion, it explains the challenges that arise from implementing the IMC program. Considering the above, the IMC implemented still remains at the stage of tactical coordination of marketing communications or an inside-out approach.

In the Gojek (Go-Ride) Yogyakarta article, which is a study of IMC with the goal of shaping brand equity, there's no explanation about the brand being the primary message, unlike many similar studies. The article also adopts a quantitative approach, focusing solely on the effects generated, without discussing that the IMC message is the brand message that shapes brand equity. Therefore, this article also remains at the first stage, namely tactical coordination of marketing communications or an inside-out approach.

Regarding the Maritime Tourism article, there's also no mention of the brand message. Although the book "IMC That Sells" (2011) explains IMC and brand, the concept of the article through the discovery circle, intent circle, and strategy circle represents an IMC strategy, yet in its execution, there's no brand serving as the message communicated to the audience. Thus, while the brand message is present in the IMC strategy, it's not implemented. Therefore, IMC has entered the second stage, the outside-in approach, but has not been carried out.

As for the other articles, RS Naili DBS, *Kapasitas Petani*, Educational Services Sector, Lemospirés *Batik*, and Gallery *Batik Sisik Melik*, the IMC message is not the brand. Hence, the IMC used remains at the first stage, the inside-out approach, or tactical coordination of marketing communications.

DISCUSSION

The Inside-Out approach represents the first stage in the implementation of IMC, and specifically, five articles, namely RS Naili DBS, Kapasitas Petani, Educational Services Sector, Lemospirés Batik, and Gallery Batik Sisik Melik, operate within this stage or the tactical coordination of marketing communications phase (Schultz & Schultz, 2004). Here, there's no brand serving as the message in IMC. The issue of marketing communication elements is only understood as promotional activities (Schultz & Schultz, 2004) in these five articles and they lack customer focus, remaining relatively simplistic in integrating various promotional elements such as advertising, public relations and publicity, sales promotion, personal selling, direct marketing, and others (Schultz & Schultz, 2004, Schultz et al., 1993; Burnett & Moriarty, 1998). Regarding the Educational Services Sector article, IMC isn't even implemented and only viewed from the consumer's perspective on educational services.

Moreover, from the communication elements used in the 10 articles, there are at least 12 elements, drawn from a combination of communication elements in existing IMC, namely advertising, personal selling, sales promotion, public relations, interactive marketing, corporate design, sponsorship, exhibition, merchandising, packaging, websites, and social media. Direct marketing and interactive marketing can basically be combined, taking the most popular, which is interactive marketing. This is inseparable from the development of communication technology that transforms media into internet-based social media (Kliatcko, 2016).

While IMC should be comprehensive, integrative, value-added, and evaluated for clarity, consistency, and maximum impact (Kitchen et al., 2004), whether complete or not, it is used in six articles, namely Salatiga Movement, Lemospirés Batik, Kapasitas Petani, Educational Services Sector, Lemospirés Batik, and Gallery Batik Sisik Melik. However, these six articles do not

Understanding 30 Years of Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) in the 2019 Indonesian Journal

explain it and only engage in IMC based on promotional "tools" as stated by Schultz and Barnes (1995), that the "inside-out" approach is traditional advertising campaigns, or referred to as approaching marketing communication planning from the needs of the marketer. However, these "tools" of promotion are already seen as strategic processes (Madhavaram et al., 2005).

Articles like Giant Ekstra, RS Naili DBS, Salatiga Movement, Gojek (Go-Ride) Yogyakarta, and YAI Campus carry out IMC programs with a brand where they don't base planning on consumers or customers (Schultz & Barnes, 1995; Kerr et al., 2008) or don't base the IMC message on brand value and meaningful dialogue (Kliatchko, 2008; Schultz & Schultz, 2004). However, brand communication in IMC must move beyond and overcome limitations in traditional ideas (Duncan, 2002). Concerning the YAI Campus article, which states that perception equality through interaction (Duncan, 2002; Estaswara 2008a), the discussion about brand value is not part of it, and it indeed neglects to seek customer input. However, brand value must be built through the formation of brand identity, which is then developed and integrated with IMC programs, the ultimate goal of which is to create brand equity (Estaswara 2008a).

Lastly, for the Maritime Tourism article, there is no IMC message about the brand. In the book *IMC That Sells* (2011), it's already shown that the brand is the most important IMC message, but the article only explains the image of Indonesia for maritime tourism. Although the discovery circle and intent circle do explain Indonesia and its maritime attributes, in the strategy circle, there's no message about the image or brand value to be built, let alone about meaningful dialogue (Kliatchko, 2005, 2008; Schultz & Schultz, 2004).

Table 3. Answering Research Questions

STUDY OBJECT	DESCRIPTION
Concept of IMC Used	IMC is marketing communication.
Communication Elements Used	Advertising, personal selling, sales promotion, public relations, interactive marketing, corporate design, sponsorship, exhibition, merchandising, packaging, websites, and social media.
Main Message in IMC	Not Brand
Inside-Out/Outside-In Approach	Inside-Out Approach

Source: Processed by the Researcher

Over the past 30 years of IMC, the concept of IMC published in various international journals does not align with the IMC practiced in Indonesia. IMC in Indonesia has evolved in line with the advancements in communication technology, particularly with the emergence of various internet-based media. Although this development is massive and global, it specifically occurs in the United States market as well (Kliatchko, 2016). However, this development has become the sole characteristic, and IMC is perceived as a specialized strategy that can be applied to all organizations, whether profit or non-profit.

Unlike Estaswara (2023), this research differs by recognizing that IMC is only regarded as marketing communication and even promotion carried out through social media. IMC is merely seen as a "tool" for marketing communication and promotion, and IMC is not considered a strategic process (Madhavaram, et al., 2005). If there is a brand mentioned in journal articles in Indonesia, then the brand is discussed separately and not related to IMC, merely evaluating its success by interviewing or surveying consumers. Whether this can be considered that the brand is the IMC message or just evaluating the IMC program, it can be said that the brand serves as an evaluation of IMC, not the IMC message.

CONCLUSION

Based on the literature review of 10 articles on IMC published in Indonesian journals in 2019, it is found that the concept of IMC is perceived as marketing communication or even promotion. Meanwhile, the communication elements include advertising, personal selling, sales promotion, public relations, interactive marketing, corporate design, sponsorship, exhibition, merchandising, packaging, websites, and social media. Furthermore, there is no brand as the IMC message. Considering these aspects, IMC falls into the inside-out approach or tactical coordination of marketing communications.

Looking at the 30-year history of IMC, it appears that IMC in Indonesian journals, which represents academic discourse, does not explore the development of the IMC concept extensively. Instead, it primarily focuses on the advancements in communication technology, particularly with the emergence of internet-based media, and implements IMC as marketing communication or promotion. This suggests that IMC is grounded in its practical application, particularly through social media

platforms.

REFERENCES

- 1) Aaker, D.A. (1996). *Building Strong Brands*. New York: Free Press.
- 2) Belch, G.E., & Belch, M.A. (2009). *Advertising and Promotion: An Integrated Marketing Communication Perspective*. 8th Edition. New York: Pearson Education.
- 3) Bettany-Saltikov, J. (2012). *How To Do a Systematic Literature Review in Nursing: A Step-By-Step Guide*. London: McGraw Hill.
- 4) Burmann, C., & Zeplin, S. (2005). Building brand commitment: A behavioural approach to internal brand management. *Journal of Brand Management*, 12, 279-300.
- 5) Burnett, J., & Moriarty, S. (1998). *Introduction to Marketing Communications: An Integrated Approach*. New York: Prentice-Hall.
- 6) Duncan, T. (2002). *IMC: Using Advertising and Promotion to Build Brands*. New York: The McGraw-Hill Companies, Inc., International Edition.
- 7) Duncan, T., & Caywood, C. (1996). The concept, process and evolution of Integrated Marketing Communication. Dalam Thorson, E. & Moore, J. (Eds). *Integrated communication: A synergy of persuasive voices*. New Jersey: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- 8) Eagle, L., Kitchen, P.J., Hyde, K. (1999). Perceptions of integrated marketing communications among marketers and agency executives in New Zealand. *International Journal of Advertising*, 18 (1), 89–119.
- 9) Estaswara, H. (2008a). *Think IMC!: Efektivitas Komunikasi untuk Meningkatkan Loyalitas Merek dan Laba Perusahaan*. Jakarta: Gramedia Pustaka.
- 10) Estaswara, H. (2008b). The Implementation Process of IMC (Integrated Marketing Communications) and Its Future Prospect in Business Practice in Indonesia: An Exploratory Comparative Study toward Four Profession Groups. *Indonesian Journal of Communication Studies*, Vol. 1(1), 73-83.
- 11) Estaswara, H. (2016). Integrated Marketing Communications (IMC) In Higher Education In Indonesia. *Polish Journal of Management Studies*, Vol. 14(1), 74-83.
- 12) Estaswara, H. (2018). Tiga Dekade Perkembangan Integrated Marketing Communications (IMC): Sebuah Literatur Review. *Guna Humas*, Vol. 1(2), 198-213.
- 13) Estaswara, H., Yuliastini, E., Kurniasari, C.W. (2023). Merek Sebagai Pesan Utama *Integrated Marketing Communication* (IMC) di Jurnal Indonesia Tahun 2020. *Jurnal Ilmu Komunikasi*, Vol. 21(1), 43-61.
- 14) Grein, A.F., & Gould, E.W. (1996). Globally integrated marketing communications. *Journal of Marketing Communications*, Vol. 2(3), 141–158.
- 15) Gould, S.J., Lerman, D.B., & Grein, A.F. (1999). Agency perceptions and practices on global IMC. *Journal of Advertising Research*, Vol. 39(1), 7–20.
- 16) Hart, C. (2018). *Doing a Literature Review: Releasing the Research Imagination*. UK, Sage Publication.
- 17) Kerr, G., & Patti, E. (2015). Strategic IMC: From abstract concept to marketing management tool. *Journal of Marketing Communications*, Vol. 21(5), 317-339.
- 18) Kerr, G., Schultz D E., Patti, E., & Kim, I. (2008). An inside-out approach to integrated marketing communication: An international analysis. *International Journal of Advertising*, 27(4), 511-548.
- 19) Kertajaya. (2012). *Wave Marketing*. Jakarta: Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- 20) Kotler, P., & Armstrong, G. (2001). *Prinsip-prinsip Pemasaran*. Jakarta: Penerbit Erlangga.
- 21) Kliatchko, J. (2005). Towards a new definition of integrated marketing communications (IMC). *International Journal of Advertising*, Vol. 24(1), 7–33.
- 22) Kliatchko, J. (2008). Revisiting the IMC construct: a revised definition and four pillars. *International Journal of Advertising*, Vol. 27(1), 133–160.
- 23) Kliatchko, J. (2016). Twenty years of IMC A study of CEO and CMO perspectives in the Asia-Pacific region. *International Journal of Advertising*, Vol. 33(2), 373–390.
- 24) Kliatchko, J., & Schultz, D.E. (2014). Twenty years of IMC. *International Journal of Advertising*, Vol. 33(2), 373-390.
- 25) Kliatchko, J., & Uttamchandani, R. (2023). A New Framework for IMC Planning. *Journal Marketing Communication*, Vol. 30(1), 1-20.
- 26) Kitchen, P.J., & Schultz, D.E. (1999). A multi-country comparison of the drive for IMC. *Journal of Advertising Research*, Vol.

Understanding 30 Years of Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) in the 2019 Indonesian Journal

39(1), 21-38.

- 27) Kitchen, P.J., & Schultz, D.E. (2009). IMC: Newhorizon/false dawn for a marketplace in turmoil? *Journal of Marketing Communications*, Vol. 15(2-3), 197-204.
- 28) Kitchen, P.J., Brignell, J., Tao Li, T., & Graham Spickett Jones, G. S. (2004). The Emergence of IMC: A Theoretical Perspective. *Journal of Advertising Research*, Vol. 44(1), 19-30.
- 29) Laurie, S., & Mortimer, K. (2011). 'IMC is dead. Long live IMC': Academics' versus practitioners' views. *Journal of Marketing Management*, Vol. 27(13-14): 1464-1478.
- 30) Lovelock, C., Wirtz, J., & Mussry, J. (2010). *Pemasaran Jasa*. Jakarta: Penerbit Erlangga.
- 31) Madhavaram, S., Badrinarayanan, V., & McDonald, R. (2005), Integrated marketing communication (IMC) and brand identity as critical components of brand equity strategy. *Journal of Advertising*, Vol. 34(4), 69-80.
- 32) Muñoz-Leiva, F., Lucia Porcu, L., & del Barrio-García, S. (2015). Discovering prominent themes in integrated marketing communication research from 1991 to 2012: a co-word analytic approach. *International Journal of Advertising*, Vol. 34(4), 678-701.
- 33) Morissan, A.M. (2010). *Periklanan dan komunikasi pemasaran terpadu*. Jakarta: Penerbit Kencana.
- 34) Rowley, J. & Slack, F. (2004) Conducting a literature review. *Management Research News*, Vol 27(6), 31-39.
- 35) Schultz, D.E., & Barnes, B.E. (1995). *Strategic brand communication campaigns*. Great Britain: NTC Business Books.
- 36) Schultz D.E., & Kitchen, P.J. (2000). *Communicating Globally: An Integrated Marketing Approach*. UK: MacMillan Education.
- 37) Schultz, D.E., & Patti, C. (2009). The Evolution of IMC: IMC in a customer-driven marketplace. *Journal of Marketing Communications*, Vol. 15(2-3), pp. 75-84.
- 38) Schultz, D.E., Kim, I., & Kang, K. (2014). "Integrated Marketing Communication Research." In *The Handbook of International Advertising Research*, edited by H. Cheng, 457-483. Hoboken, NJ: Wiley.
- 39) Schultz, D.E., & Schultz, H. (2004). *IMC: The Next Generation*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- 40) Schultz, D.E., Tannenbaum, S. & Lauterborn, R. (1993). *The New Marketing Paradigm: Integrated Marketing Communications*. Illinois: NTC Business Books.
- 41) Šerić, M. (2016). Content analysis of the empirical research on IMC from 2000 to 2015. *Journal of Marketing Communications*, 24(4):1-39..
- 42) Sierra-Correa, J.R., & Kintz, C. (2015). Ecosystem-based adaptation for improving coastal planning for sea-level rise: a systematic review for mangrove coasts. *Marine Policy*, Vol. 51, 385-393.
- 43) Shimp, T. (2003). *Periklanan Promosi: Aspek Tambahan Komunikasi Pemasaran Terpadu*. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- 44) Tjiptono, F. (2008). *Strategi Pemasaran*, Edisi III. Yogyakarta: CV. Andi Offset
- 45) Watono, A., & Watono, M. C. (2011). *IMC That Sells*. Jakarta: Gramedia Pustaka Utama.